

Modification of Montmorillonite Nano-clay with Butyl Acrylate (BuA) and Methacrylate (MMA) by ATRP. Blends with Poly(BuA-co-MMA)

M. Karesoja¹, H. Jokinen¹, E. Karjalainen¹, P. Pulkkinen¹, M. Torkkeli², A. Soininen³, J. Ruokolainen³ and H. Tenhu¹

1. Laboratory of Polymer Chemistry, Department of Chemistry P.O.Box 55, FI-00014 University of Helsinki

2. Department of Physical Sciences, P.O. Box 64, FI-00014 University of Helsinki

3. Optics and Molecular Materials, Department of Engineering Physics and Mathematics, P.O. Box 5100 FI-02015 Helsinki University of Technology

Corresponding author email: mikko.karesoja@helsinki.fi

SUMMARY

ATRP initiator was covalently bound to montmorillonite clay platelets via silylation reactions. The initiator clay was used to polymerise BuA and MMA on the clay surface. Modified clay was blended with poly(BuA-co-MMA). Mechanical properties of the composites were studied by dynamic mechanical analysis showing a considerable improvement of properties with increasing clay content.

Keywords: nanocomposite, montmorillonite, dynamic mechanical thermal analysis

INTRODUCTION

Clay polymer nanocomposites have been heavily studied recently, because of the excellent optical, barrier, dielectric, flame retardant, and mechanical properties.[1-7] Also clay as such is cheap, environmentally friendly and well available filler material for polymer nanocomposites. The properties of nanocomposites are strongly dependent of the separation of the silica layers of the clay particles. This is due to the fact that dispersion of clay as individual platelets increases the interfacial area between the clay and the matrix polymer.

Most commonly used layered silicate is montmorillonite clay. Montmorillonite clay is compounded of micron sized particles. These micro particles are constructed of small platelets (thickness ~1nm and width 100-200nm). Platelets have permanent negative charge and are held together by cations such as Na⁺ and Ca²⁺.

The difficulty of the use of inorganic filler materials with polymer matrices is to achieve homogenous mixing of the filler. Thus the modification of the filler material is essential. The most traditional way to modify clay is to ion exchange the small cations in the clay gallery to the organic ammonium salts [8]. This causes the expansion of the space between the platelets and facilitates the exfoliation of the clay. Also this turns the clay more hydrophobic and thus it is more compatible with hydrophobic polymers. Another method is silylation reactions. Organochlorosilanes can react with –OH groups on the external and internal surfaces clay [9]. More recently the clay surfaces are modified by using *in situ* free radical polymerisation techniques such as atom transfer radical

polymerisation technique (ATRP) [10], reversible addition-fragmentation polymerisation [11] and nitroxide mediated polymerisation [12].

In this work our aim has been covalently bound an ATRP initiator on the surfaces of montmorillonite clay via silylation reactions. The clay modified with ATRP initiator is further used to polymerise n-butyl acrylate (BuA) and methyl methacrylate (MMA) to achieve exfoliated clay structure. This modified clay was then mixed with the matrix polymer (poly(BuA-co-MMA)) with similar chemical composition than the grafts on the clay surface.

EXPERIMENTAL

Montmorillonite clay was organically modified by exchanging the cations with octadecylammoniumchloride. The ATRP initiator 11-(2-Bromo-2-methyl)propionyl-oxy-undecyl trichlorosilane was covalently bound on the montmorillonite surface. Polymerisation reactions of BuA and MMA on the clay surface were carried out in a bulk monomer solution or in dimethylsulphoxide, DMSO. The matrix polymer of BuA and methyl methacrylate was prepared in detergent free emulsion polymerisation. The ratio of BuA:MMA in feed was 75%/25%.

The blends of polymer modified montmorillonite or pure montmorillonite were prepared by solution casting and the contents of the clay in the composite films were 1-5 wt % respectively.

The exfoliation of clay was studied with the transmission electron microscopy, TEM, and small angle x-ray scattering, SAXS. Storage modulus E' , loss modulus E'' and $\tan \delta$ were measured as a function of temperature and also stress-strain measurements were performed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The success of each step of the synthesis was ensured by infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Figure 1 shows the FTIR spectra of the initial montmorillonite and the reaction products. The spectrum of the matrix copolymer poly(BuA-co-MMA) is also included. The initial montmorillonite shows a characteristic peak at 1043 cm^{-1} originating from Si-O-Si. A clear shoulder is observed at 910 cm^{-1} which corresponds to -Si-OH groups. Also weak peaks at 3620 cm^{-1} and 1629 cm^{-1} are visible. The peak at 3620 cm^{-1} corresponds to free -OH groups. Ion exchanged clay shows clear -CH₂- peaks at 2920 and 2851 cm^{-1} , in addition to the characteristic peaks of montmorillonite. After the attachment of the initiator, clear -CH₂- peaks (2926 and 2854 cm^{-1}) can be seen but the intensities are lower than in the previous spectrum. Carbonyl peak at 1736 cm^{-1} has appeared, this indicating that the attachment of the initiator group was successful. After polymerization, the characteristic peaks of both poly(BuA-co-MMA) and montmorillonite can be seen.

Figure 1. FTIR spectra of different reaction steps. 1. Pure montmorillonite 2. Ion exchanged clay 3. ATRP initiator clay 4. Polymer modified clay 5. Matrix polymer poly(BuA-co-MMA).

Figure 2 shows TGA thermograms for the pure clay, ion exchanged clay, clay initiator, and the polymer modified clay. In the case of the initial montmorillonite 12% mass loss can be observed below 100°C. This is due to the evaporation of water from the clay. In the case of ion exchanged clay decomposition of organic substance, octadecylammoniumchloride occurs in the range 190-560°C and the total mass loss is 42%. In the case of the initiator clay the decomposition takes place in the range 210-570°C and the total mass loss is 27%. The total mass loss is smaller than in the case of ion exchanged clay, this is most probably because of the loss of octadecylammoniumchloride during the attachment of the initiator on the clay surfaces. As noted above, also FTIR showed smaller $-\text{CH}_2-$ peaks for the initiator clay than for ion exchanged clay. Similar behavior of an organic salt during silylation has been reported by Ogawa [9]. The decomposition of the polymer modified clay takes place in the temperature range 280-530°C and the total mass loss is 87%. TGA data agrees favourably with the FT-IR results and shows that all synthesis steps have been successful.

Figure 2. TGA thermograms of 1. montmorillonite 2. initiator clay 3. ion exchanged clay and 4. Polymer modified clay.

The exfoliation was studied by TEM and SAXS. TEM showed well dispersed and exfoliated structure for clay polymer modified in DMSO (fig 3.). In the case of clay polymer modified in bulk monomer solution TEM showed mainly exfoliated structure but also some larger clay particles still existed. SAXS data in figure 4 supports well the TEM data. In the case of polymer clay modified in DMSO no diffraction peaks can be seen. This suggests exfoliated structure. The polymer clay modified in the bulk monomer solution shows clear diffraction peak around 0.33 \AA^{-1} . Pure clay shows diffraction peak at 0.43 \AA^{-1} .

Figure 3. TEM image of polymer modified clay (polymerised in DMSO).

Figure 4. SAXS of unmodified clay 1 and polymer modified montmorillonites (polymerised in bulk (2) and in DMSO (3))

Figure 5 shows the storage modulus as a function of temperature for composite films which were prepared using clay modified in DMSO. The storage modulus values are high because the polymer is in the glassy state. Around -30°C the storage modulus decreases rapidly this is the glass transition temperature, T_g , of the material. The glass

transition temperature of different samples is surprisingly close to each other even though the clay content is increased. In many cases the glass transition has been reported to increase when the clay content increases. Wheeler et al reported that more incompatible clays increase the T_g more than more compatible ones [13]. In our case the clay surface has been modified with poly(BuA-co-MMA) which structure is very similar with the matrix polymer. This leads to the situation where the compatibility between the clay and the matrix polymer is excellent and the T_g is not affected.

Figure 5. Storage modulus as a function of temperature.

Figure 6 Shows stress strain curves for composite films. The pure polymer film is showing lowest stress values of all films. Adding 2% and 5% of unmodified montmorillonite clay improves the mechanical properties only slightly. When adding polymer modified clay to the matrix polymer the mechanical properties are improved more already when clay content of film is 2% and dramatic change in mechanical properties can be seen when the clay content is 5%. The more pronounced improvement in the mechanical properties is due to the exfoliation and good dispersion of clay particles in the matrix. Unmodified clay is not very well dispersed and exists as larger particles in the matrix.

Figure 6. Stress strain curves for composite films. 1. Matrix polymer Poly(BuA-co-MMA) 2. Composite containing 2% of unmodified clay 3. Composite containing 5% of unmodified clay 4. Composite containing polymer modified clay 2% 5. Composite containing polymer modified clay 5%.

CONCLUSIONS

Polymers can be bound covalently on the montmorillonite platelets by ATRP reactions. The exfoliation of the clay was studied by SAXS and TEM. These techniques revealed exfoliated composite structure was achieved. Polymer modified clay was mixed with matrix polymer poly(BuA-co-MMA) and composite films with good mechanical properties were obtained. The polymer modification enhances the homogenous mixing of the clay to the matrix and facilitates the exfoliation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financial support was received from Finnish Funding Agency for Technology and Innovations, TEKES.

References

1. LeBaron P.C.; Wang Z.; Pinnavaia T.J. *Appl Clay Sci* 1999, 15, 11-29
2. Wang H.-W.; Shieh C.-F.; Chang K.-C.; Chu C.-C., *J Appl Polym Sci* 2005, 97, 2175-2181
3. Gilman J.W. *Appl Clay Sci* 1999, 15, 31-49
4. Kim S.; Wilkie C. A. *Polym. Adv Tech* 2008, 19, 496-506

5. Costache M. C.; Heidecker M. J.; Manias E.; Camino G.; Frache A.; Beyer G.; Gupta R. K.; Wilkie C. A. *Polymer* 2007, 48, 6532-6545
6. Wang Z.; Massam J.; Pinnavaia T.J. In *Polymer-Clay Nanocomposites*; Pinnavaia T.J.; Beall G.W., Eds.; Wiley series in polymer science; Wiley; Chichester, 2000; Chapter 7, pp 127-149
7. Rao Y.Q.; Pochan J.M. *Macromolecules* 2007, 40, 290-296
8. Vaia R. A.; Teukolsky R. K.; Giannelis E. P. *Chem. Mater.* 1994, 6, 1017-1022
9. Ogawa M.; Okutomo S.; Kuroda K. *J Am Chem Soc* 1998, 120, 7361-7362
10. Böttcher H.; Hallensleben M. L.; Nuß S.; Wurm H.; Bauer J.; Behrens P. *J Mater Chem* 2002, 12, 1351-1354
11. Salem N.; Shipp D. A. *Polymer* 2005, 46, 8573-8581
12. Weimer M.W.; Chen H.; Giannelis E.P.; Sogah D.Y. *J Am Chem Soc* 1999, 121, 1615-1616
13. Wheeler P.A.; Wang J.; Mathias L.J. *Chem Mater* 2006, 18, 3937-3945